

Mono-Chelates of Copper(II) with 5(3)-Methylpyrazole-3(5)-Carbohydrazide

NITYANANDA SAHA* and KRISHNA M. DATTA

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 2 February 1981, revised 28 May 1981, accepted 22 July 1981

Mono-chelates of copper(II) with 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carbohydrazide (MPCH) have been synthesised and physico-chemically characterised. The ligand MPCH primarily functions as a neutral (ONN) tridentate through the (pyrazolyl) ring nitrogen, the amidic nitrogen and the amidic oxygen (of the hydrazide component) in forming the species of empirical composition $Cu(MPCH)_X_2 \cdot nH_2O$ [$X = Cl, Br, ClO_4, NO_3, BF_4$ or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4$; $n = 0$ or 2]. Magnetic and spectral data indicate polymeric octahedral structures for these seemingly monomeric species, where the amidic nitrogen atom of the ligand in each monomer forms a bridge with its neighbouring unit through coordination to the Cu(II) ion of the adjacent molecule and thus the ligand behaves effectively as a tetradentate one.

THE remarkable antituberculous activity of ISONIAZID has initiated a substantial amount of research^{1,2} on the transition metal complexes of pyridine carboxylic acid hydrazides and their derivatives. It, however, appears from a survey of literature that no work has been done on the ligating properties of pyrazole based acid hydrazides. As a part of our programme³ of investigating the coordinating properties of biologically important substituted diazoles we recently reported⁴ the nickel(II) complexes of neutral and deprotonated 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carbohydrazide (I, MPCH). The present communication reports the isolation and physico-chemical characterisation of monochelate complexes of Cu(II) with empirical composition $Cu(MPCH)_X_2 \cdot nH_2O$.

(I)

Experimental

The preparation and characterisation of the ligand, MPCH has been described earlier⁴.

Preparation of the complexes: $Cu(MPCH)_X_2 \cdot nH_2O$ [$X = Cl, Br, ClO_4, NO_3, BF_4$ or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4$; $n = 0$ or 2]: A solution of the hydrated copper(II) salt $CuX_2 \cdot nH_2O$ (0.01 mole) in ethanol (water in case of the sulphate) was added to a hot solution of the ligand (0.01 mole) in the same solvent. The resulting green solution ($pH \approx 3$) was heated on a water bath for about 10 mins with occasional stirring and then cooled to room temperature. The green/blue compound (Table-1), which separated in each case, was filtered off, washed with water and alcohol and dried over fused calcium chloride. The copper content of the complexes was determined iodometrically after decomposing the complex with a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids. Halogen was estimated as silver halide and sulphate as $BaSO_4$. Nitrogen was determined microanalytically. The molar conductances, the magnetic susceptibilities, the diffuse reflectance spectra and the ir spectra of the complexes were recorded as described earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes along with their pertinent physical properties are given in Table 1. These copper(II) complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The perchlorate and fluoborate complexes, however, are soluble in methanol and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	%Cu		%Nitrogen		%Anion(X)		Λ_M^* ($cm^{-1}cm^3mole^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} in B.M. 302°K
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found		
$Cu(MPCH)Cl_2$	green	23.12	23.26	20.39	20.41	25.85	25.60	23.7	1.63
$Cu(MPCH)Br_2$	green	17.46	17.51	15.41	15.32	43.97	43.65	26.2	1.70
$Cu(MPCH)(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	blue	14.48	14.50	12.77	12.84	16.18**	16.00	70.0	1.74
$Cu(MPCH)(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	green	17.47	17.40	23.10***	23.23	—	—	75.1	1.67
$Cu(MPCH)(BF_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	green	15.37	15.46	13.55	13.64	—	—	60.4	1.78
$Cu(MPCH)SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	blue	18.92	18.87	16.68	16.55	28.51	28.38	****	1.58

*in $10^{-3}M$ solution in DMF at 30°; **percentage of chlorine; ***including nitrogen present in nitrate;

****could not be measured due to the low solubility of the complex.

all are fairly soluble in donor solvents like DMF, DMSO etc. The molar conductance values ($\Lambda_M \sim 60-75 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$) of the perchlorate, nitrate and fluoborate complexes in DMF approach those expected for 1:1 electrolytes in the said solvent⁶; the values ($\Lambda_M \sim 25 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$) obtained for the halide complexes in the same solvent are, however, significantly less. The conductance values suggest that the anions presumably bonded to the Cu(II) ion (supported later by ir data) in the solid state are partially released in solution; the Λ_M values for the perchlorate, nitrate and fluoborate complexes can be reconciled in terms of a solvolysis equilibrium of the type :

The somewhat low magnetic moments for most of the copper(II) species suggest^{7,8} antiferromagnetic interaction between the Cu(II) ions arising from dimerisation or polymerisation in the solid state either through $\text{Cu}^{+2}-\text{Cu}^{+2}$ interaction or through ligand participation.

in general, are characterised by a broad band in the region 13.5 - 16.4 kK.

An additional spectral band in the region 25.6 - 27.0 kK (Table 2) has often been observed in the electronic spectra of the complexes both in the solid state and in solution. The ϵ_{max} values of this band for the solution spectra is fairly low for L→M CT band and as such, their origin may be attributed^{7,11} to the presence of dinuclear species in the complexes.

IR spectra : The ir spectrum of the ligand, 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carbohydrazide, in the solid state, shows a strong band covering the region 3340-3200 cm^{-1} which is attributable to the hydrogen-bonded NH and NH_2 stretching frequencies. The other characteristic ir bands appearing at 1640(s), 1530(s), 1270(w), 880(s) and 665(s) cm^{-1} may be assigned respectively as the amide I, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ (of the pyrazole ring), amide (III), $\nu\text{N}-\text{N}$ (of the hydrazide residue) and the inplane deformation of the pyrazole ring.

The negative shift of the amide I band (appearing at $\sim 1610 - 1625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) by about 15 - 30 cm^{-1} and the

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	State	Absorption maxima in kK (ϵ_{max})
Cu(MPCH)Cl ₂	Reflectance DMF	13.9 ; 26.7 14.3 (47.8) ; 25.6 (229.9)
Cu(MPCH)Br ₂	Reflectance DMF	14.5 ; 26.7 14.3 (55.3) ; 25.6 (273.8)
Cu(MPCH)(ClO ₄) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	16.1 ; 26.3 14.0sh (69.5) ; 14.5 (70.0) ; 26.3 (231.2)
Cu(MPCH)(NO ₃) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	Reflectance DMF	14.7 ; 26.6 13.5 (64.1) ; 16.7sh (49.8) ; 25.6 (283.0)
Cu(MPCH)(BF ₄) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	15.6 ; 26.7 16.4 (46.6) ; 26.3 (279.8)
Cu(MPCH)SO ₄ · 2H ₂ O	Reflectance	16.1 ; 27.0

The diffuse reflectance spectra (Table 2) of the complexes are characterised by a broad asymmetric band appearing in the range 13.9 - 16.1 kK. The blue or green copper(II) complexes are, in most cases, known to have tetragonally distorted octahedral structures⁹. In D_{4h} symmetry three transitions¹⁰ from the ground state, viz., ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (ν_3) are predicted from the energy level diagram. The splitting of the octahedral 2E_g and ${}^2T_{2g}$ states increases with tetragonal components of the crystal field. As the energy of the ${}^2A_{1g}$ state increases, a situation may come up in which this state is sufficiently close to ${}^2B_{2g}$ and 2E_g states for the three transitions not to be properly resolved in the spectrum⁹. Thus the appearance of a single broad band (in the range 13.9 - 16.1 kK) in the spectra of the present Cu(II) complexes suggests that all the three expected transitions lie within one broad envelope and that distortion is not large from octahedral symmetry, though the extent of distortion is not known.

The electronic spectral data (Table 2) of the methanol or DMF solution of the complexes indicate that there is no appreciable change in the stereochemical environment of the complexes in solution; the spectra,

positive shift of the amide III band (appearing at $\sim 1290 - 1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) by about 20 - 40 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of the complexes compared to those of the free ligand points to the participation of the hydrazide group in bonding through the oxygen atom. It is pertinent to point out here that the negative shift of the amide I band would have been much more had there been no hydrogen bonding in the free ligand. Such a conclusion receives support from the observation that the ir spectrum of the acetonitrile solution of the ligand shows amide I band at 1670 cm^{-1} due to the breaking of the hydrogen bonds.

Excepting for the halide complexes, the ir bands in the 3 μ region are somewhat complicated as the NH stretching bands are covered by the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ bands arising from the presence of lattice water in the complexes and no useful conclusion can be made. However, in the spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{MPCH})\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br), the appearance of NH and NH_2 stretching vibrations at a much lower frequency region ($\sim 3260-3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) compared to that in the uncomplexed ligand unequivocally points to the involvement of the terminal nitrogen of the hydrazide group in bonding to the copper(II) ion. Thus the present study indicates that the hydrazide

TABLE 3—ANION FREQUENCIES WITH PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS

Comp'lex	Anion bands (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments
Cu(MPCH)(ClO ₄) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	1150(w) 1120(m) 1080(s)	Components of ν(Cl-O) in C _{3v} symmetry
Cu(MPCH)(NO ₃) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	1390(s) 1315(m) 830(s)	Components of ν ₃ } in C _{2v} symmetry ν ₂
Cu(MPCH)(BF ₄) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	1110(m) 1070(m) 1040(s)	Components of ν ₃ in C _{3v} symmetry
Cu(MPCH)SO ₄ · 2H ₂ O	1170(sh) 1110(s) 1050(m) 995(s)	Components of ν ₃ } in C _{2v} symmetry ν ₁

residue of the ligand is bonded to the copper(II) ion through the amide-oxygen and amino-nitrogen atom forming a five membered chelate ring as suggested by earlier workers^{1,12}.

An interesting feature of the ir spectra of these complexes is the large (+)ve shift of the νN-N of the hydrazide residue by about 120 - 140 cm⁻¹ which indicates² that both the nitrogen atoms of the hydrazide component of the ligand are bonded to the metal thereby producing a polymeric structure through the coordination of the amidic nitrogen of each molecular unit, Cu(MPCH)X₂, to the copper(II) ion present in the neighbouring unit. The subnormal magnetic behaviour and the insolubility of the complexes in water and common organic solvents may be recalled at this point, in support of the validity of such a proposition which is also in line with those suggested for several other metal complexes of hydrazine derivatives¹³. The positive shift of the νC=N (by ~15 - 20 cm⁻¹) and in-plane deformation (by ~15 - 25 cm⁻¹) of the pyrazole ring as compared to the uncomplexed ligand indirectly indicate the tertiary nitrogen atom of the pyrazole ring as a possible bonding site; the conclusion is in good agreement with earlier observation¹⁴ on the metal complexes of other N-heterocycles and is also in conformity with crystallographic studies¹⁵ of many pyrazole-metal complexes. The far ir data on the chloride complex shows strong bands at 270, 300 and 390 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to the νCu-Cl¹⁶, νCu-N (ring)¹⁷ and νCu-O¹⁸ respectively.

Diagnostic ir frequencies of the polyatomic anions (Table 3) indicate clearly the mono-dentate nature of perchlorate¹⁹, nitrate²⁰ and fluoroborate²¹ ions; the sulphate ion, on the other hand, is present as a bridging bidentate one²². It may be concluded on the basis of above discussion that the ligand 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carbohydrazide, in forming monochelates of Cu(II) salts primarily functions as a tridentate (ONN) one acting through the ring nitrogen, aminic nitrogen and amidic oxygen. Of the three other coordination positions in these six-coordinate copper(II) complexes two are occupied by anions (X) and finally the coordination sphere is completed by the coordination of the amidic nitrogen from the neighbouring mono-chelate unit

thereby producing a polymeric three dimensional net work(II) and thus the ligand (MPCH) behaves effectively as a tetradentate one.

(II)

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor S. E. Livingstone of the University of New South Wales, Australia for kindly providing them with the reflectance spectra of the compounds.

References

1. K. NAGANO, H. KINOSHITA and H. HIRAKAWA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1964, 12, 1198.
2. R. C. AGGARWAL, T. PRASAD and B.N. YADAV, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 899 and references therein.
3. N. SAHA and N. C. GAYEN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19A, 229 and references therein.
4. N. SAHA and K. M. DATTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, (in press).
5. N. SAHA and S. KAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 195.
6. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
7. M. KATO, H. B. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 64, 99.
8. P. W. BALL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 4, 361.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 357.
10. D. E. BILLING and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2141.
11. R. D. WILLET, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2482.
12. R. M. ISSA, M. F. ELSHAZLY and M. F. ISKANDER, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1967, 354, 90; R.C. AGGARWAL and T. R. RAO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1978, 40, 1177.
13. R. C. AGGARWAL and K. K. NARANG, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 9, 1413 and references therein.
14. J. R. FERRARO, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1969, 23, 160; R. C. PAUL, R. S. CHOPRA and G SINGH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 14, 105.
15. C. W. REIMAN, A. SANTORO and A. D. MIGHELL, *Acta Cryst. B*, 1970, 26, 521.

SAHA & DATTA : MONO-CHELATES OF COPPER(II) WITH 3(5)-METHYLPYRAZOLE-5(3)-CARBOHYDRAZIDE

16. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations", E. Arnold, London, 1967, p. 308.
17. F. MANI and G. SCAPACCI, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1976, 16, 163.
18. R. C. AGGARWAL and T. R. RAO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1978, 40, 171.
19. B. J. HATHAWAY and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 3091.
20. N.F. CURTIS and Y.S. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 804.
21. N. N. GREENWOOD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3811.
22. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963, p. 161.